

OCEAN:ICE News – March 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Happy Spring!

We're entering spring with the two OCEAN:ICE moorings successfully deployed in South Sandwich Trench and we're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE. This month's newsletter features the updated OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI), engaging Climate Coffees, and a chance to review the proceedings of a few OCEAN:ICE events, in case you couldn't attend or wish for a recap.

Moreover, get to know our featured researcher of the month, mark your calendars for the upcoming OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting 2024, stay informed about the upcoming Climate Coffees and where you can find OCEAN:ICE in action at various events.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more exciting news in April!

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

Updated OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI)

OCEAN:ICE aims to create a collaborative atmosphere that welcomes diversity of thought and allows everyone to thrive, no matter their background or characteristics and uphold excellence in the science that we do together.

OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI) (D9.9.) was recently updated and published on the [OCEAN:ICE Community](#) in [Zenodo](#) and on the [OCEAN:ICE website](#).

You may access OCEAN:ICE EDI policy [here](#).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. Further down in the *Upcoming Climate Coffees* section you may find the lineup for upcoming Climate Coffees, and if you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Proceedings: 10th EuroGOOS International Conference 'European Operational Oceanography for the Ocean we want – Addressing the UN Ocean Decade Challenges', 3-5 October 2023, Galway, Ireland

[The 10th EuroGOOS International Conference](#) addressed all aspects of operational oceanography and its societal relevance discussed priorities in the context of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030.

OCEAN:ICE held a poster presentation "OCEAN:ICE interactions and exchanges and their climate and Earth impacts" at the 10th EuroGOOS International Conference in Galway, Ireland. You may find the information about the OCEAN:ICE poster presentation in the ['Proceedings of the 10th EuroGOOS International Conference 'European Operational Oceanography for the Ocean we want – Addressing the UN Ocean Decade Challenges'. 3-5 October 2023, Galway, Ireland'](#), pages 357-360.

Proceedings: SO-CHIC and OCEAN:ICE Joint Project Conference, 24-25 October 2023, Sorbonne University, Paris, France and online

[SO-CHIC](#) and [OCEAN:ICE](#) Joint Project Conference 2023 was a collaboration between the two projects. The goal of the jointly organised scientific conference was to bring together Southern Ocean and cryosphere scientists not only from OCEAN:ICE and SO-CHIC, but also from other projects funded by the European Union, the European Space Agency, UK Research and Innovation, as well as other related projects from the EU Polar Cluster and beyond to foster scientific exchanges and collaborations. The conference was divided into the following segments:

- What is next (for SO-CHIC)? What's new: research questions, calls, programmes;
- Engaging with stakeholders;
- Coordination of field work/modeling across existing projects;

Additionally, the poster session was organised as well as the breakout groups aimed at discussing the opportunities for collaboration, coordination, and continuation of work, identifying gaps for future research. Everyone from SO-CHIC and OCEAN:ICE and additional projects was invited to attend this joint conference. The programme included presentations from related projects, the EU Polar Cluster and beyond. Post-docs and PhD students were encouraged to participate in the conference as well the Early Career Researchers breakfast in the morning of the 25th of October 2023.

As promised in the [OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting 1 \(MS18\) report](#), we have made the [proceedings of the SO-CHIC and OCEAN:ICE Joint Project Conference 2023](#) available in the [OCEAN:ICE Zenodo community](#) [Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System](#) as well as on the [OCEAN:ICE website](#).

Researcher in the Spotlight: Qing Qin

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Qing Qin, a Post-Doctoral Researcher at Northumbria University.

Read Qing's interview [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting, 23-25 September 2024, Copenhagen & online

Save the dates for the OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting, 23-25 September 2024, which will be kindly hosted by the Danish Meteorological Institute in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Stay [tuned](#) for more information.

Photo by [Nick Karvounis](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Upcoming Climate Coffee

[Tian Tian](#) on [Cooler Arctic surface temperatures simulated by climate models are closer to satellite-based data than the ERA5 reanalysis](#)

4 April 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Tian Tian, Danish Meteorological Institute

Cooler Arctic surface temperatures simulated by climate models are closer to satellite-based data than the ERA5 reanalysis

4 April 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET

Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Happening in Spring

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 10-12 April 2024, [UN Ocean Decade Conference](#), Barcelona
- 14-19 April 2024, [EGU General Assembly](#), Vienna & online
- 7-18 May 2024, [Southern Ocean Summer School](#), Cargese

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

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<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

Danish
Meteorological
Institute

**Northumbria
University**
NEWCASTLE

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